

The European Approach to AI from a Recommender System Perspective

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Introduction

The European Commission (EC) has acknowledged the importance that Artificial Intelligence (AI) plays in forming Europe's future, identifying AI as the most strategic technology of the 21st century¹.

The EU is a community of law, having as its primary focus not only to achieve technological excellence, but also to ensure fundamental human rights and create trust in the use of technology. Indeed, in the last decade, the EU has been a global pioneer in producing landmark pieces of technology-related legislation, with the most indicative examples being the General Data Protection Regulation² (GDPR) and the Network and Information Security Directive³ (NISD). Recently, the emphasis has been placed on devising a human-centric approach to AI technology. However, achieving this goal entails several challenges which are still to be addressed. Tackling these challenges, as well as coming up with the appropriate regulations for doing so, are of major importance to the EC.

With a recent proposal on a *Regulation Laying Down Harmonised Rules on Artificial Intelligence*⁴ (*EU Regulatory Framework for AI*), the EC aims at introducing the first ever legal framework on AI, which will identify specific risks for AI, provide a collection of high-risk application domains, propose specific requirements that AI systems should meet when used in such domains, and define obligations for users and providers with respect to testing, risk management, documentation, and human oversight of AI systems throughout their entire lifecycle. The *EU Regulatory Framework for AI* defines different risk levels for AI applications, ranging from minimal risk (e.g., spam filters), limited risk (e.g., chatbots), high risk (e.g., candidate scoring in recruitment), and unacceptable risk (e.g., autonomous weapons). What clearly emerges from all these efforts by the EC is the need for an AI which behaves in a responsible way. A clear and globally accepted definition of responsibility for AI systems is still under development by the academic and industrial communities. Responsibility in turn can be understood in terms of notions such as **fairness, security and privacy, explainability**, and reproducibility. Although reproducibility is a fundamental issue in AI research and its industrial application, we will not cover it here since it is a common requirement in modern science, therefore not specific for AI.

Here, we discuss the remaining three important dimensions of the human-centric approach, which the EU envisions for the development, deployment, and use of AI systems. In fact, they are very well stated and formulated in the EC document "Building Trust in Human-Centric Artificial Intelligence"⁵ where seven key requirements are introduced: *Human Agency and Oversight; Technical Robustness and Safety; Privacy and Data Governance; Transparency; Diversity, Non-discrimination, and Fairness; Societal and Environmental Well-being; Accountability*. **We attempt to provide the European scene for each of the three dimensions, under the lens of Recommender Systems (RSs)**. Given their user-centric nature, RSs are fully touched by the principles and rules stated in the documents published by the EC, and this is one of the main reasons why they represent an interesting work bench for their application. Issues related to fairness, security and privacy, explainability (and reproducibility) may affect a RS at training and run time (see Figure 1).

¹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/ALL/?uri=CELEX%3A52018SC0137>

² <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>

³ <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/topics/nis-directive>

⁴ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52021PC0206>

⁵ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/communication-building-trust-human-centric-artificial-intelligence>

Figure 1. Recommender Systems life cycle.

To better understand the impact of responsible RSs, we consider two crucial application scenarios, namely **news and jobs recommendation**.

Case study news: Citizens increasingly rely on online content and recommender systems to consume *news*. Most democratic theories agree on the value of citizens coming into contact with opinions, debates, or ideas they disagree with or even dislike. This implies that simply designing a news RS to provide the news most relevant to the user, as is common now, is not enough. The lack of any bias or discrimination in the recommendation, as well as some degree of coverage, timeliness, and coherence, must be guaranteed. At the same time, explanatory mechanisms must be provided to the users to keep them informed about the motivations behind the recommendation. In order to trust the system, implementing defense strategies against attacks to the recommendation algorithm is necessary. We note that these concerns are not restricted to traditional news media. Recent leaks from social media companies such as Facebook have shown the importance of considering the potential risks of fragmentation, spread of harmful information (including misinformation), and even manipulation of elections. Depending on editorial and societal values, different types of fairness may be considered in the news domain. E.g., in some cases, it may be more relevant to represent (and amplify) minority voices,

while in others a representation that is proportional to the percentage of the population a viewpoint represents is vital. In the former case, it may be relevant to move beyond polarized pro/con stances and classical sentiment analysis, to obtain a more nuanced representation of a viewpoint. If users are given the autonomy afforded by increased transparency and control, this may create a tension between the editorial intention to diversify the news recommender and a user's ideological preferences. Recent work discusses the possibility of designing simulations which allow news platforms to assess the recommendations on the system level.

Moreover, proper interface design of news recommenders can support the user to become more aware of the system's inner workings and its influence on their media consumption. Interface design should make clear which defaults or presets the system has (e.g., initially applying a certain algorithm, even if users can change this in a control panel), so the user can decide whether or not recommendations are in line with their preferences. Users should also be able to switch off personalization and investigate the effects of such changes to the resulting recommendations. More engaged users can change the default settings, while default settings could be set towards nudging the user to be more diverse.

Case study recruitment: Recommender systems have also significant impact in the world of work and, in particular, in *hiring and recruitment* processes where their use is becoming more and more prevalent [3]. Interestingly, an estimated 98% of Fortune 500 companies use some form of AI in their recruitment processes. Even more so, European companies are also moving to hiring practices that often rely on some form of AI-based recommendation. Recommender systems in social network platforms may also impact the workforce, as such systems have the power to shape the pool of candidates where job advertisements are recommended. As beneficial as such systems might appear from a recruiter's perspective, they may discriminate against certain groups or individuals by reflecting or reinforcing human or society structural bias. Such discrimination may have severe consequences for underrepresented groups in granting access to the labor market. An example of such a group, which is of high importance to the EC, are women in Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) professions, who are severely and persistently underrepresented. The economic and social consequences of the gender gap in STEM have been extensively acknowledged [4]. It is thus not a coincidence that the EC lists AI systems used in the context of *"employment, workers management and access to self-employment"* as high-risk in Annex III (point 4) of the *EU Regulatory Framework for AI*.

The EC proposed regulation points out that AI should be used in the EU in compliance with the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights⁶, including the right not to be discriminated against, the respect for private life, and the protection of personal data. It also stresses the *"obligations for ex ante testing, risk management and human oversight of AI systems to minimize the risk of erroneous or biased AI-assisted decisions in critical areas such as education and training, employment, important services, law enforcement and the judiciary"* (Section 3.5). High-risk AI systems should meet specific legal requirements in relation to data management, documentation, human oversight, transparency, robustness, accuracy and security. According to Article 10 (Data and Data Governance), *"training, validation and testing data sets shall be subject to appropriate data governance and management practices"* which shall concern in particular (among others), *"examination in view of possible biases"* and the *"identification of any possible data gaps or shortcomings, and how those gaps and shortcomings can be addressed"*. On the other hand, Article 15 is devoted to accuracy, robustness, and cybersecurity: high-risk AI systems must achieve all three throughout their entire lifecycle to a

⁶ https://ec.europa.eu/info/aid-development-cooperation-fundamental-rights/your-rights-eu/eu-charter-fundamental-rights_en

satisfactory degree based on state-of-the-art security and privacy-preserving measures, including pseudonymisation or encryption. The regulation makes it also clear that “AI systems should be sufficiently transparent, explainable and well-documented” (Article 13: Transparency and Provision of Information to Users).

Fair Recommender Systems

Despite the many provisions proposed by the EC regarding AI fairness, in reality, RSs have been shown to provide different recommendation quality to different users, depending on various characteristics, such as gender, age, ethnicity, or even personality traits [7,11,6,9,10]. Such behavior conflicts with the above mentioned goals and is likely to yield unfairness.

Definitions. It is common to distinguish between *individual fairness* and *group fairness*. The former means that similar users are treated in a similar fashion (e.g., users with similar skills receive job recommendations

Figure 2. Different categories of biases and their interplay.

within the same pay grade). The latter means that different groups of users defined by some sensitive or protected attribute (e.g., gender, age, or ethnicity) are treated in the same way. Accordingly, unfairness is defined as “The system systematically and unfairly discriminates against certain individuals or groups of individuals in favor of others.” [5].

Categories of Biases. Unfairness is commonly caused by societal or statistical biases, the former referring to the divergence between how the world should be and how it actually is, the latter to the discrepancy between how the world is and how it is encoded in the system. Such biases can occur at different levels in the recommendation pipeline (see Figure 2). They can be present already in the *data* the algorithms are trained on (e.g., an unbalanced dataset with respect to representation of different genders), they can be amplified by the *algorithms* or in created *model* (e.g., reinforcing stereotypes), or they can originate from a wide range of users' *cognitive biases* (e.g., serial position, anchoring, and decoy effects) [3].

Bias Mitigation Strategies. To alleviate existing biases, several techniques can be adopted. Focusing on data and algorithm/model bias, the most common ones are *data rebalancing* (e.g., upsampling the minority group of users in the dataset, or subsampling the majority group), *regularization* (e.g., including a bias correction term in the loss function of machine/deep learning algorithm), and *adversarial learning* (e.g., training a classifier that tries to predict the sensitive attribute from the user--item interaction data and modify the data or recommendation algorithm to make this classifier perform as poorly as possible).

While much research has been devoted to uncovering and mitigating biases in RSs, both within and outside the EU, there still exist many research gaps. The most pressing ones can be summarized as follows:

1. Several metrics of fairness have been proposed in the literature. However, a comprehensive (formal and comparative) study of their strengths and limitations is still missing⁷. Even whether they reflect what humans perceive as unfair - possibly depending on their cultural background, values, and beliefs - has not yet been subject of deep investigations.

⁷ <https://wires.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/widm.1356>

2. Likewise, a deep understanding of capabilities and limitations of existing techniques for mitigating bias through their systematic evaluation is missing.
3. From an algorithmic perspective, novel methodologies to debias state-of-the-art RS algorithms, which are predominantly based on deep learning, are needed.
4. An investigation of potential economic and social consequences of biases resulting from the use of RSs adopted in high-risk areas (e.g., in recruitment) is needed.
5. Currently, fairness is typically addressed from the perspective of the system's end users. Instead, we should consider multiple stakeholders in the recommendation process, including content producers, content consumers, and platform providers.
6. From a legal perspective, we need provisions with respect to data quality, concrete specifications to whom the obligations to not violate EU non-discrimination law applies, and effective mechanisms for auditing RSs for legal compliance. In general, an interdisciplinary perspective is needed, involving collaboration between researchers with technical expertise and law expertise, to mitigate bias without jeopardising fundamental human rights.

Security and Privacy for Recommender Systems

Over the years, privacy in AI applications has become a dominant concern in the EU. Following the rules stated in the GDPR, statistical analyses, machine learning (ML) techniques, and AI strategies have to be applied by keeping in mind the new privacy challenges that may limit the uptake of these applications. All risks related to the privacy of users are even more evident when we think about the applications of RSs

where user models are built around personal data.

Issues. It turns out that solving the problem of data fragmentation and isolation while complying with the GDPR is a major challenge for RS researchers. Actually, preserving users' privacy is not as easy as limiting data collection since a privacy threat may happen at any stage of the data cycle. The model itself stores precious information able to predict future user preferences and behaviors. The main target of privacy attacks in a RS is the confidentiality of the users' sensitive data. Privacy-preserving ML aims to equip ML with defense measures for protecting user privacy and data security. It should be distinguished from secure ML, which attempts instead to preserve integrity and availability of a ML system from intentional attacks like adversarial or poisoning attacks.

Figure 3. Information flow over the network in four ML architectures. Solid lines represent training data flow, dashed lines represent model parameters flow.

While handling users' privacy concerns, FL faces challenges such as communication costs, unbalanced data distribution and device reliability and security issues (e.g., *model poisoning*, *indirect information leakage*, and *Byzantine*

adversaries). Despite its original formulation, in [14] the concept of FL is extended to a more comprehensive idea of privacy-preserving decentralized collaborative ML techniques, both for horizontal federations (where different datasets share the same feature space but are different in training samples) and vertical federations (where different datasets share the training samples but differ in feature space). Thanks to tunable federation approaches in recommendation scenarios, users can be more aware of and decide which data they share [1].

Unfortunately, while FL can offer significant practical privacy improvements over centralized approaches, there is still no formal guarantee of privacy. This is where other techniques and algorithms come to the stage to help and enforce the privacy protection mechanisms also in recommendation scenarios. In particular, we refer to *Differential Privacy*, *Secure Multi-party Computation*, and *Homomorphic Encryption*.

Adversarial Attacks and Defense. Notwithstanding the great success of machine/deep learning models, recent studies have shown that they are not immune to security threats from adversarial use of AI, and the same holds for RSs [2]. An adversary can attack a ML model at two main stages of the learning pipeline, during training or production. These two categories of attacks are respectively known as (i) *training-time attack* (a.k.a. *causative* or *poisoning attack*) and ii) *inference-time attack* (a.k.a. *exploratory* or *evasion attack*).

- *Poisoning attack.* Data poisoning attacks are realized by injecting false data points into the training data with the goal to corrupt/degrade the model (e.g., the classifier).
- *Evasion attack.* Unlike poisoning attacks, evasion attacks do not interfere with training data. They adjust malicious samples during the inference phase. These attacks are also named *decision-time attacks* referring to their attempt to evade the decision made by the learned model at test time.

Adversarial examples created for image classification tasks are empowered based on continuous real-valued representation of image data (i.e., pixel values), but in RSs, the raw values are user/item identifiers and ratings that are discrete. Hence, adversarial perturbations are added to one of the following data: (i) directly to the user profile (i.e., user rating profile), (ii) user and item model parameters in a latent factor model; (iii) and (iv) embeddings representing side information of user and items, respectively.

Together with attack strategies, defense mechanisms against adversarial attacks have been developed in the last years. They can be classified into detection methods and methods seeking to increase the robustness of the learning model. At the heart of the robust optimization method is the assumption that every sample in the training data can be a source for adversarial behavior. It applies a zero sum-game between the prediction and attack adversaries. The ultimate goal in robust optimization is that the prediction model will perform equally well with adversarial and clean inputs.

Explainable Recommender Systems

Recommender systems operate as artificial advice givers. However, people using the system may not understand how the conclusion was reached and when it is appropriate to adopt the advice, or in contrast, when to critique it. The *Regulation Laying Down Harmonised Rules on Artificial Intelligence* consequently indicates that explanations need to supply human oversight of high-risk systems.

However, in our view there are three main scientific challenges to overcome before compliance is possible, namely: **a)** how to ensure that explanations are human-understandable and support appropriate trust; **b)** how to build explainable AI (w.r.t. explanation confidence and model complexity); and **c)** how to validate the goodness of explanations.

Understandability. Human oversight is not feasible if explanations are not understandable by people, and “*Interpretability*” has been qualified as the degree to which a human can understand the cause of a decision [12]. Understanding is rarely an end-goal in itself, and it is often more useful to measure the effectiveness

of explanations in terms of a specific notion of usefulness or *explanatory goals* such as improved decision support or (appropriate) user trust [13] -- minimizing both over and under-reliance on system advice. Furthermore, both the characteristics of the people (e.g., expertise, cognitive capacity) and the situation (e.g., which other people are affected, or which variables are influential) place different requirements on which explanations are useful, e.g., resulting in different presentational choices (e.g., with regard to modality, degree of interactivity, level of detail). Simply put, "One size does not fit all".

Building eXplainable AI (XAI). A large number of methods for XAI have been developed, for a breadth of models and types of data. However, many of them do not (by design) support users in fully understanding the capacities and limitations in a way that would support appropriate trust. We identify two particularly limiting barriers: limited model confidence and high model complexity.

- *Confidence.* We argue that for sufficient human oversight, RSs have to be aware of their knowledge limits not only on the prediction (global and instance) level but on the explanation level as well. Consequently, RSs need to provide confidence information for each prediction and explanation; and they need to clarify how the confidence information has been obtained or computed.
- *Complexity.* While it is commonly (but erroneously) believed that there is a trade-off between accuracy and interpretability, this is not strictly true. In many cases, several models can offer comparable accuracy performance, but some are more human-understandable. Complexity can be mitigated by selecting the simpler model, and by developing interactive interfaces such as those we have developed in our work which: 1) adapt the generated explanations to different factors; 2) allow the people using the system to see how the factors influence the explanations (transparency), as well as modify the contribution of the factors (control).

Evaluation of Explanations. User studies are in our view *indispensable* for evaluating human performance and understanding. However, to date they are relatively rare in the literature, likely due to their cost. Explanations have also been subjected to automated evaluations, modeled as penalties and constraints in optimization problems, sparsity of the model, monotonicity with respect to a variable, or decomposability into sub-models, etc. However, so far there have been no standardized metrics developed. As for ML (Precision, Recall, F-measure, AUC), perhaps this is also because there is no single ideal objective (e.g., accuracy versus succinctness). Nevertheless, we hope in the coming years to see benchmarking of such metrics as we see in challenges such as Kaggle, CLEF, and SemEval.

Conclusions

The wide adoption of AI algorithms and systems calls for the definition and realization of a responsible approach to AI. In this respect, by following the documents and legal frameworks proposed over the last years by the European Commission, some technological issues and trends emerge. We require AI systems to be fair, secure and privacy-preserving, interpretable and explainable. Due to their human-centric nature and the high impact they have on decisions we make in daily life, recommender systems offer an interesting point of view to investigate technical and algorithmic solutions for the next generation of responsible AI applications that comply with EU regulations and directives. In fact, the notions of bias and fairness, security and privacy, and explanation are of paramount importance if we want to build a trustworthy technology aimed at helping us in day-to-day decisions. In this article we outline the steps that have already been taken in this direction, as well as indicate what we see as the challenges ahead before we can fulfill the spirit of the legal requirements. We hope that this will serve as a useful roadmap for practitioners and researchers alike.

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